

ANTI-MICROBIAL AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF VARIOUS EXTRACTS OF *CISSUS QUADRANGULARIS*. L STEMS

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ABSTRACT

Plants are involved in a complex network of interactions with microorganisms; some of those are beneficial, others detrimental, but the former are by the largest and still widely unexplored part. The *Cissus quadrangularis*, invites the attention of the researchers worldwide for its pharmacological activities such as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity, anti-osteoporosis activity, and bone healing activity. To study the Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Microbial activity of various extracts of *Cissus quadrangularis* Extraction of the active constituents from the *Cissus quadrangularis* L. Stem by using Ethyl acetate and Methanol solvents by Soxhlet. Methanol extract showed greatest inhibition on pathogen *Serratia marcescens* and *E-coli* with a zone of inhibition of 25 mm, in a concentration of 200 µg/ml. The CQE extract showed greatest inhibition on pathogen *E- Coli* with a zone of inhibition of 16.02 mm, in a concentration of 200 µg/ml. For Red Blood Cell Stabilization Method, compared to Methanol extract Ethyl acetate extract shows more percentage protection. For remaining all the 3 tests/ methods like Inhibition of Protein Denaturation method, α-amylase inhibitory assay, Glucose uptake by yeast cells, the obtained results are compared with each other extracts Methanol extract shows the dominance over Ethyl acetate extract. The Ethyl acetate and methanol extracts of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. Stem produced effective results in anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial activity compared with the standard drugs.

Keywords: Anti-inflammatory, Anti-microbial, *Cissus quadrangularis* L., Soxhlet Extraction.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are defined as those that are frequently used to treat and prevent specific diseases and illnesses. Plant-based medications are widely used because they are safe, easy to obtain, and provide additional benefits. Herbal remedies can contain entire plants or are mostly made from the leaves, flowers, bark, roots, and seeds of plants. These drugs are taken orally and applied topically. The beneficial physiological activity that these plants provide to the human body is attributed to their bioactive phytochemical contents.

Throughout history, humans have relied on nature to provide them with basic necessities such as food, clothing, tastes, fertilizers, housing, transportation, and medical treatment. Medicinal plants being a significant part in the healthcare management of significant portions of the world population. This is especially the case in developing countries where herbal medicine had its impact from olden days. Both developed and developing countries are seeing an increase in the research and development of these plants potential medical benefits as well as their economic value.

Plants engage in a complicated web of interactions with microbes, of which some are advantageous and others harmful, but the majority of these interactions are still mostly unknown. It has been demonstrated thus far that helpful microbes can be used to reduce or replace chemicals.

The Nalleru plant (*C. quadrangularis*) has been found to contain a wide range of important constituents, such as flavonoids like genistein, daidzein, and quercetin; triterpenoids like friedelin; vitamin 'C'; stilbene derivatives like quadrangularin-A, resveratrol, and piceatannol; iridoids like 6-O-meta-methoxy-benzozyll catapol; phytosterols like β -sitosterol and calcium; and picroside and pallidol. The plant stem contains the following components: protein, calcium oxalate, 31 methyl tritriacontanoic acid, β -amyrins, β -sitosterol, ketosterol, phenols, tannins, taraxeryl acetate, taraxeroliso-pentadecanoic acid, calcium ions, and phosphorus.

Rat's ear and paw edema induced by ethyl phenylpropionate, carrageenan, and arachidonic acid, respectively, were reduced by *Cissus quadrangularis* extract¹. Because of the high level of antibacterial activity of *C. quadrangularis*, methanol extracts of the plant's stems were further investigated through GC-MS analysis to discover the bioactive ingredients².

Researchers from all over the world are interested in the pharmacological properties of *Cissus quadrangularis* because of its analgesic³, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and free radical scavenging properties, as well as its ability to mend bones^{4,5} and prevent osteoporosis. Hemorrhoids, gas, scurvy, and menstruation problems are all treated using the fresh stem and leaves of *Cissus quadrangularis* (CQ). Cysteine proteases (Cp) are present in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes and are broadly dispersed in living creatures and Cp from *C. quadrangularis* extract⁶. This article's goal is to explore and attribute the anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial properties of many *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem extracts.

MATERIALS

Plant Materials

The plant material used for this work is the stem of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. was collected from surroundings of the Vijayawada.

The Common Pathogenic Microorganism

The experimental methods employed six pathogenic microorganisms which are common in general: 3Gram -ve (*Escherichia coli*, NCIM 2256), 3Gram +ve (*Micrococcus luteus*, NCIM 2871), 3 Gram +ve positive (*Bacillus subtilis*, NCIM 2710), and 3Gram –ve (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, NCIM 2037), and 3 Gram –ve (*Serratia marcescens*, NCIM 2078) Every examined strain was obtained from the National Collection of Industrial Microorganisms (NCIM) and is a reference strain.

Instruments

Incubator (37 °C), refrigerator (4 °C to 18 °C), autoclave, hot air oven, precision electronic balance, grinder, micropipette (100 to 1000 µl), Bunsen burner, matches, and inoculating loop are the instruments utilized for this job.

Chemicals

Peptone, agar, sodium chloride, beef extract, Muller Hinton agar, ethyl acetate, ethanol, methanol, chloroform (research lab fine chemical industry), and dimethyl sulfoxide are the chemicals employed in this work.

Consumables

Sterilized cotton buds, sterile paper discs with a 0.5 mm thickness (autoclave), sterile cotton, and cotton plugs are the supplies needed for this task.

METHODS

Preparation of Extract

Plant materials that were recently collected, such the stem of *Cissus quadrangularis L.*, were dried. The plant materials were pounded into a fine powder after being separately dried in the shade. The *Cissus quadrangularis L.* powdered plant materials were kept separately in the refrigerator at 4 °C in airtight jars. Soxhlet's apparatus was used to extract 15 gm of dried powder stem of *Cissus quadrangularis L* with 125 ml of ethyl acetate for 6 hours (or) until the plant material became colorless. A rotating vacuum evaporator was used to eliminate the remaining trace amount of solvent, yielding a concentrated extract. The *Cissus quadrangularis L* stem was extracted using methanol solvents using the same procedure. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used to prepare *Cissus quadrangularis* stem solvent extracts at different concentrations (100, 200 µg/ml).

Screening of Antimicrobial Activity

Media for Bacterial Organisms

Furthermore, 10 ml of sterile distilled water were combined with 0.1 g of dextrose and steam sterilized for 15 minutes. 400 ml of sterile water and 15.2 g of Muller Hinton Agar were combined, then autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes under 15 pounds of pressure. After mixing and cooling, the two contents were layered to a height of roughly 4 mm on sterile petri plates. After allowing them to settle at room temperature, they were used.

Preparation of inoculum

The bacterial inoculum was created by inoculating a pure culture of the test organism into 5 milliliters of sterile nutritive broth. The mixture was then incubated at 37 °C for two to eight hours, or until moderate turbidity occurred. By comparing the turbidity of the inoculum to the 0.5 McFarland standard, which is equal to 10⁸ CFU/ml of cell density, the inoculum was standardized.

Antibacterial activity by agar disc diffusion method

Each *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extract's antibacterial activity was assessed using a modified Kirby Bauer disc diffusion method⁷. The Muller Hinton Agar medium was used to distribute the bacterial organism's broth cultures on petri plates, and the microbe's broth culture was carried out in a laboratory setting. A 5 mm sterile filter paper disc was used to evaluate the extracts after

being impregnated with 100, 200 µg/ml ethyl acetate, and methanol extracts of the stem of *Cissus quadrangularis*. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for about 24 hours to observe the antibacterial activity of the extracts, following a brief period of time for them to dry at room temperature.

Screening of Anti-Inflammatory activity

Red blood cell membrane stabilization test

Human red blood cells (HRBCs) were used to evaluate the anti-inflammatory properties of *C. quadrangularis* stem extract *in vitro*. Blood samples from human subjects were provided, and they were mixed equally with sterile Alsever's solution. After centrifuging this blood at 3000 rpm, the packed cells were separated. 10% v/v suspension was made with isosaline after the packed cells were cleaned with an isosaline solution. Every solution aside from the extracts were introduced to the control to get it ready. This HRBC suspension was mixed with different amounts of plant extracts (methanol and ethanol acetate), 1 mL of 7.4 pH phosphate buffer, 2 mL of hyposaline, and 0.5 mL of HRBC suspension. Following a 30-minute incubation period at 37°C, each experiment combination was centrifuged at 3000 rpm. The amount of hemoglobin was measured using a spectrophotometer at 560 nm after the supernatant liquid was decanted. The proportion of hemolysis was calculated by assuming that the control group's hemolysis was 100%.

Percentage Protection = $100 - (\text{OD Control} / \text{OD Sample}) \times 100$.

Inhibition of Protein Denaturation Method

The Gambhire⁸ method was used for the protein denaturation experiment, with a few minor adjustments as reported by Gunathilake⁹. 0.02 ml of extract, 4.78 ml of phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 6.4), and 0.2 ml of 1% bovine albumin made up the reaction mixture (5 ml). For five minutes, the mixture was heated to 70°C. The control was phosphate buffer solution. After the mixture cooled, the turbidity at 660 nm was measured with a UV/VIS spectrometer (Optima, SP-3000, Tokyo, Japan).

The following formula was used to compute the % inhibition of protein denaturation:

% Inhibition of Denaturation = $100 \times (1 - A2/A1)$, where A1 denotes the adsorption of the control sample and A2 the adsorption of the test sample.

α -amylase inhibitory assay

Various amounts of the extract were made in DMSO in order to evaluate the *C. quadrangularis*-*in-vitro* α -amylase inhibitory activity. To prepare the substrate, two milligrams of starch, 0.2 milliliters of 0.01 M CaCl₂, and 0.5 milliliters of tris-HCl buffer (pH 6.9) were added. Each test tube received 0.2 ml of different plant extract concentrations and 0.1 ml of pig pancreatic amylase in tris-HCl buffer (2 units/ml) after the substrate mixture had been boiled for five minutes. Using the same solutions as the extract, a control was created. After 10 minutes of incubation at 37°C, the wavelength of the reaction mixture was measured at 595 nm using a spectrophotometer. The supernatant was then added to stop the process. The inhibitory activity of α -amylase was determined using formula¹⁰.

$$\% \alpha\text{-amylase inhibition} = \{(A595 \text{ Control} - A595 \text{ Sample}) / A595 \text{ Control}\} \times 100$$

Glucose uptake by yeast cell

For the purpose of conducting studies on the uptake of glucose, commercial baker's yeast was suspended in 10% w/v distilled water. Distinct dosages of *C. quadrangularis* were cultured for 60 minutes at 37°C in test tubes that held one milliliter of glucose solution (5–25 mM). The amount of glucose in the supernatant was estimated by spinning test tubes for five minutes at 5000 rpm after incubation. By measuring the glucose with a control sample at 520 nm, a UV Spectrophotometer was employed. For yeast cells, the following formula was used to calculate the percentage increase in glucose uptake.

$$\% \text{ Increase in glucose uptake} = \{(A520 \text{ Control} - A520 \text{ Sample}) / A520 \text{ Control}\} * 10$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process's initial phase, gathering plant material from the stem of *Cissus quadrangularis*, produced the results. When the material is gathered, its weight (without drying) is typically around 2 kg. After the process is finished, the net weight (naturally dried) is around 1 kg. The dehydrated material is pounded into a fine powder and then stored in an airtight container. Eventually, roughly 759 grams of powder was obtained.

For the purpose of making the methanol and ethyl acetate extracts, we removed 30 grams (15 gm + 15 gm) of powder from these 759 grams. The extract is extracted using the Soxhlet device, and the rotatory evaporator dries the extracted material completely.

The final quantities of extracts obtained are shown in Table-1

Table No-1 Quantity of extracts obtained from the extraction

S. No	Name of Extract	Quantity used	Quantity obtained
1.	Ethyl acetate Extract	30 grams (15+15 gms)	920 mg
2.	Methanol Extract	30 grams (15+15 gms)	3000 mg

Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Red Blood Cell Membrane Stabilization Test

The Human Red Blood Cell (HRBC) technique shows positive activity for the anti-inflammatory effects of *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem extracts *in vitro*, with methanol and ethyl acetate extracts showing positive action at varied dosages (100, 200 µg/ml).

Fig No.1 Collected and Centrifuged Blood Samples

Table No-2 Absorbance of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts and control

S. No	Name of the Extract	Concentrations	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Methanol	1.507	1.367
2.	Ethyl acetate	1.080	0.613

The formula for calculating Percentage Protection is shown below

$$\text{Percentage Protection} = 100 - (\text{OD sample} / \text{OD Control}) \times 100$$

The results show a positive effect, for both extracts, the Percentage Protection increases with the increase in concentration. The results are shown in Table No -3

Table No-3 Percentage Protection of *Cissus quadrangularis*. L stem extracts

S. No	Name of the Extract	Percentage Protection%	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Methanol	38%	44%
2.	Ethyl acetate	56%	75%

The aforementioned information demonstrates how *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts help to stabilize the membrane of human red blood cells. According to the findings, the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem's ethyl acetate extract exhibits a greater percentage of protection than the stem's methanol extract.

Inhibition of Protein Denaturation Method

In vitro examination of the anti-inflammatory effects of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. stem extracts show favorable action for the suppression of the protein denaturation, including ethyl acetate and methanol extracts at many concentrations (100, 200 µg/ml). The extracts' absorbance compared to the control is shown in Table No. 4 below.

Table No-4 Absorbance of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts and control

S. No	Name of the Extract	Concentrations	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Ethyl acetate	0.064	0.094
2.	Methanol	0.138	0.110

The formula used to calculate % protein denaturation inhibition is shown below: -

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of Denaturation} = 100 \times (1 - A_2/A_1)$$

The percentage of protein denaturation inhibition increases with concentration for both extracts, indicating a beneficial effect, according to the results. Compared to ethyl acetate extracts,

methanol extract exhibits a higher proportion of inhibition against protein denaturation. Table 5 presents the findings.

Table No-5 Percentage Protein denaturation inhibition of *C quadrangularis*. L stem extracts

S. No	Name of the Extract	Percentage Protection%	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Methanol	80%	92%
2.	Ethyl acetate	12%	64%

The data above demonstrate the beneficial effects of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts on the suppression of protein denaturation. The findings indicate that the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem's methanol extract exhibits greater prevention of protein denaturation than the stem's ethyl acetate extract.

α-amylase inhibitory assay

Anti-inflammatory properties of *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem by *in vitro* studies of inhibition of α-amylase inhibitory experiment, using extracts such as ethanol and methanol extracts at varying doses (100, 200 µg/ml) exhibit positive action. The absorbance of the extracts and the control is shown in Table No. 6 below.

Table No-6 Absorbance of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts and control

S. No	Name of the Extract	Concentrations	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Ethyl acetate	0.138	0.153
2.	Methanol	0.156	0.176

The formula used to calculate % α-amylase inhibition is shown below-

$$\% \alpha\text{-amylase inhibition} = \{(A595 \text{ Control} - A595 \text{ Sample}) / A595 \text{ Control}\} \times 100$$

The proportion of α-amylase inhibitory assay increases for both extracts as the concentration increases, indicating a beneficial effect, according to the data. Compared to ethyl acetate extracts, methanol extract exhibits a higher proportion of α-amylase inhibitory test. The outcomes are displayed in Table No. 7

Table No-7 Percentage of α -amylase inhibition of *Cissus quadrangularis*. L stem extracts

S. No	Name of the Extract	% α -amylase inhibition	
		100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
1.	Methanol	47%	66%
2.	Ethyl acetate	30%	44%

As evidenced by the data presented above, *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts are advantageous to the α -amylase inhibitory test. The findings indicate that the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem methanol extract exhibits higher percentage α -amylase inhibition than the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem ethyl acetate extract.

Glucose uptake by yeast cells

The anti-inflammatory properties of *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem extracts through *in vitro* studies such as methanol and ethyl acetate extracts, when used at varying quantities (100 and 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), exhibit beneficial effects on yeast cells' ability to absorb glucose. Table No. 8 below displays the extracts' absorbance along with the control.

Table No-8 Absorbance of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts and control

S. No	Name of the Extract	Concentrations	
		100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
1.	Ethyl acetate	0.035	0.050
2.	Methanol	0.045	0.065

The formula used to calculate the % increase of glucose uptake by yeast cells is shown below-

$$\% \text{ Glucose uptake by yeast cells} = \{(A_{520} \text{ control} - A_{520} \text{ sample}) / A_{520} \text{ control}\} * 100$$

The results show a positive effect, with the percentage of glucose taken up by yeast cells increasing with concentration for both extracts. Compared to ethyl acetate extracts, methanol extract demonstrates a higher proportion of glucose absorption by yeast cells. The outcomes are displayed in Table No. 9.

Table No-9 Percentage Increase of glucose uptake by yeast cells of *C quadrangularis*. L stem extracts

S. No	Name of the Extract	% Glucose uptake by yeast cells	
		100 µg/ml	200 µg/ml
1.	Methanol	50%	83%
2.	Ethyl acetate	16%	66%

The data above demonstrate how *Cissus quadrangularis* stem extracts improve yeast cells' ability to absorb glucose. The findings indicate that the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem methanol extract exhibits a higher percentage of α -amylase inhibition than the *Cissus quadrangularis* stem ethyl acetate extract.

Anti-Bacterial Activity: The Antimicrobial activity of the extract (**Ethyl Acetate Extract of *C quadrangularis*. L stem**) was performed through paper disc methods.

Table 10 displays the outcomes of the ethyl acetate extract's anti-bacterial activity against the different gram-positive bacterial strains. According to the table, the extract's level of antibacterial activity against the various diseases varied slightly. With a 10 mm zone of inhibition for ampicillin standard, the CQE extract demonstrated the highest level of inhibition against the pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus*. At the same dose, all other species, including *Bacillus subtilis* and *Micrococcus luteus*, showed slightly less inhibition, measuring 8 or 7 mm. At a dosage of 100 µg/ml, the least inhibition was seen on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Micrococcus luteus*, with an inhibition zone measuring 6 mm.

Table No-10 Antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of CQE extract against gram positive microorganisms

CQE extract Concentration (µg/ml)	Zone of inhibition of various gram +ve bacteria (mm)		
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>
Standard (Ampicillin)	8 ±0.3	10 ±0.4	7 ±0.3
100 µg/ml	6 ±0.3	6 ±0.3	6 ±0.4
200 µg/ml	7 ±0.4	8 ±0.4	7 ±0.3

Table No. 11 displays the outcomes of the ethyl acetate extract's antibacterial efficacy against the different gram-negative bacterial strains. According to the table, the extracts' modest varying levels of antibacterial activity against the various infections were observed. With a 40 mm zone of inhibition at an ampicillin standard concentration, the CQE extract exhibited the highest level of inhibition against the pathogen *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In the same concentration, *Serratia marcescens* and *E. coli* showed slightly less inhibition, either by 18 or 24 mm. At a dosage of 100 µg/ml, the least inhibition was seen on *Serratia marcescens*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with an inhibition zone of 5 mm.

Table No-11 Antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of CQE extract against gram negative microorganisms

CQE extract Concentration (µg/ml)	Zone of inhibition of various gram -ve bacteria (mm)		
	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	<i>E-coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Standard (Ampicillin)	18 ±0.3	24 ±0.4	40 ±0.3
100 µg/ml	7 ±0.3	7 ±0.3	5 ±0.4
200 µg/ml	8 ±0.4	16 ±0.4	7 ±0.3

The results of the methanol extract's antibacterial activity against the several positive bacterial strains are shown in Table No. 12. The table shows a modest variation in the extract's antibacterial efficacy against the different diseases. With a zone of inhibition of 19 mm, the CQM extract showed the maximum level of inhibition against the pathogen *Micrococcus luteus* at a dosage of 200 µg/ml with a zone of inhibition of 19 mm, the CQM extract showed the maximum level of inhibition against the pathogen *Micrococcus luteus* at a dosage of 200 µg/ml. With the exception of *Micrococcus luteus* and *Bacillus subtilis*, all other species had marginally less inhibition in the standard (ampicillin) concentration, measuring 13 or 10 mm. The least amount of inhibition was observed on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Micrococcus luteus* at a dosage of 100 µg/ml, with an inhibition zone measuring 7 or 6 mm.

Table No-12 Antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of CQM extract against gram positive microorganisms

CQM extract Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Zone of inhibition of various gram + ve bacteria (mm)		
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>
Standard (Ampicillin)	9 \pm 0.3	13 \pm 0.4	10 \pm 0.3
100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	6 \pm 0.3	7 \pm 0.3	6 \pm 0.4
200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	8 \pm 0.4	9 \pm 0.4	19 \pm 0.3

The results of the antibacterial effectiveness of the ethyl acetate extract against the various gram-negative bacterial strains are shown in Table No. 13. The table shows that there was a modest variation in the extract's antibacterial efficacy against the different diseases. The CQM extract showed the highest level of inhibition against the pathogens *Serratia marcescens* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with a zone of inhibition of 35 mm and an ampicillin standard concentration. At a 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration, all other species, except for *Serratia marcescens* and *E. coli*, showed slightly less inhibition, measuring 25 mm. At a dosage of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the least inhibition was seen on *Serratia marcescens*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with an inhibition zone of 5 mm.

Table No-13 Antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of CQM extract against gram negative microorganisms

CQM extract Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Zone of inhibition of various gram -ve bacteria (mm)		
	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	<i>E-coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Standard (Ampicillin)	35 \pm 0.3	28 \pm 0.4	35 \pm 0.3
100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	20 \pm 0.3	9 \pm 0.3	18 \pm 0.4
200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	25 \pm 0.4	25 \pm 0.4	16 \pm 0.3

The above-obtained results regarding the Anti-Inflammatory and antimicrobial activity by using both the Ethyl acetate and Methanol extracts show positive activity.

Anti- Inflammatory Activity

The anti-inflammatory properties of *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem have been studied *in vitro* using a variety of tests and methodologies, and both ethyl acetate and methanol extracts demonstrate this effect.

- Ethyl acetate extract exhibits a higher percentage of protection in the Red Blood Cell Stabilization Method as compared to methanol extract.
- The findings of the other three tests/methods, which include the α -amylase inhibitory assay, the inhibition of protein denaturation method, and the glucose uptake by yeast cells, are compared with each other's extracts. Ethyl acetate extract is outperformed by methanol extract.

These are final results that can be clearly understood that methanol extract shows more potent activity compared to ethyl acetate extract in exhibiting anti-Inflammatory properties.

Anti-Microbial Activity

The anti-microbial activity of *Cissus quadrangularis* was tested using both methanol and ethyl acetate extracts. *Cissus quadrangularis* L stem on three microbes that are gram-positive and three that are gram-negative. The standard medication for evaluating the antimicrobial activity was ampicillin.

- At a 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration, the CQM (methanol) extract exhibited the highest inhibition against the pathogens *Serratia marcescens* (-ve) and *E. coli* (-ve), with a zone of inhibition of 25 mm.
- With a zone of inhibition of 19 mm and a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the CQM extract exhibited the highest level of inhibition against the pathogen *Micrococcus luteus* (+ve).
- With a zone of inhibition of 16.02 mm and a dose of 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the CQE extract demonstrated the highest level of inhibition on the pathogen *E. coli* (-ve).
- At a 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ dose, the CQE extract exhibited the highest inhibition against the pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* (+ve), with a zone of inhibition measuring 8.04 mm.

This shows that anti-microbial activity increases with the increase of concentration. As we know ampicillin is a standard anti- microbial drug that shows more activity compared to the CQ extracts. When the comparison between the extracts, methanol extract shows more inhibition of the growth of organisms, whether it is gram-negative or gram-positive bacterial organisms compared to ethyl acetate extract.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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